
Radiofrequency impedance matching of STM junction for reflection measurements

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Abstract

In this thesis, we propose a new method that is aimed to detect the local variations of the superconducting order parameter on the atomic scale by integrating a scanning tunneling microscope with novel gigahertz reflectometry techniques. Calculations on the reflection coefficient of the GHz signal show the benefits and limitations of using an impedance matching circuit that transforms the impedance of the tunnel junction into the characteristic 50 Ohms. We pay attention to the effect of the losses in the matching circuit for both lumped and distributed element cases. Simulations show that these loss effects can be partially compensated for a distributed-element impedance matching circuit.

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Introduction

1.1 Motivation

From the free electron gas to the most complex many-body interaction systems, the field of condensed matter aims to understand systems of electrons at low energies. The interactions originated from the material that the electrons populate are the key element that makes the field of condensed matter a thrilling subject, full of a variety of profound ideas. In a solid, electrons can often be thought as single independent particles in an effective potential, giving rise to the electronic band theory. This theory seeks to describe the behavior of electrons that populate a solid, correctly predicting such behaviour as a metal, semiconductor or insulator. It is, however, based on the non-interactivity of the system, considering electrons as independent entities. For this reason, it fails to predict many macroscopic phenomena that emerge from the collective behaviour of the electrons, namely, that of superconductivity.

Heike Kamerlingh Onnes' original research in 1911 opened the doors to superconductivity, the field that has guided much of our understanding of quantum phases of matter up to this day. More recently, much attention has been given to the so-called high-temperature superconductors, due to having a superconducting critical temperature above nitrogen's boiling point [1]. These materials are classified within the group of unconventional superconductors, whose behavior is not yet fully understood microscopically. Unconventional superconductors, as well as strongly disordered superconductors, are characterized by a fragile superconducting phase that can be locally destroyed by phase fluctuations well below the critical temperature in which electrons start to bound in pairs [2, 3]. The strong effect of phase fluctuations can lead to a segregation of the order parameter into regions with different superfluid density above the critical temperature. Direct observation of the spacial inhomogeneity of the superfluid density for most of these materials could provide a broader picture to describe their behaviour [3].

The aim of this thesis is to present a new method to study locally the superfluid density of unconventional and strongly disordered superconductors. These materials have been predicted to host an inhomogeneous complex order parameter (Sec.1.2) above the critical temperature associated to the superconducting state. The method discussed in this report is based upon reflection measurements performed through a scanning tunneling microscope (STM) at GHz frequencies (Sec.1.3). By analysing the ratio between the reflected and sent signals at high enough frequencies, it is possible to obtain information about the superfluid density of the sample. Furthermore, the possibility of scanning the sample can directly probe the spacial inhomogeneity of the order parameter. To this end, we present different ways of achieving a measurable signal by adding an extra circuit between the tip-sample system of the STM and the output electronics of the setup: the impedance matching circuit (Ch.2). Several impedance matching methods are discussed with special emphasis on the losses and avoiding their effect.

1.2 Unconventional and strongly disordered superconductors

Superconductivity is characterized microscopically by two principal ingredients: the formation of Cooper pairs and the creation of a condensate with a macroscopic phase coherent state. Below certain temperature, the electrons start to bound in pairs leading to a gap opening, Δ , in the electronic band structure. Hence, the superconducting condensate is described by a complex order parameter, $\Psi = \Delta e^{i\phi}$, defined by an amplitude, Δ , and a phase, ϕ . In conventional superconductors, which follow Bardeen-Cooper-Shrieffer (BCS) theory [4], the energy cost of twisting the phase of the condensate, given by the superfluid stiffness, J , is much higher than the gap energy, Δ . Therefore, the superconducting-normal transition occurs when Δ goes to zero [5] at the critical temperature, T_c . Conventional superconductors form a coherent condensate ground state immediately after the formation of Cooper pairs.

There are two main types of fluctuations of the order parameter [2]: amplitude and phase fluctuations. Here we focus on phase fluctuations, which are the ones that can destroy the superconducting state for the materials that we target in this work. Phase fluctuations can be divided in two principal groups: 1) Classical phase fluctuations, whose effect on the system is determined by the superfluid density $n_s(T)$. The smaller n_s , the bigger the role of the phase fluctuations. 2) Quantum phase fluctuations, which come from the number-phase uncertainty relation. Big number fluctuations between neighboring regions lead to phase coherence between such regions.

Due to the rigidity of the BCS ground state, fluctuations on the order parameter of

conventional superconductors will only play a role at temperatures that are infinitesimally close to T_c . Consequently, there is a very small region where these fluctuations exist* and they are assumed to be relatively unimportant.

Apart from conventional superconductors, there are many others that do not follow this description. This is the case for unconventional and strongly disordered superconductors, among others, which cannot be explained through BCS theory. For the first type, the low density of superconducting carriers will enhance the superfluid stiffness J to be smaller than the pairing energy Δ associated to the pseudogap[†] state [2, 3, 7]. As a result, phase fluctuations may have a significant effect on determining the superconducting transition. This behaviour has been studied in underdoped high-temperature superconductors [2, 8]. There is a similar scenario for the strongly disordered s-wave superconductors such as TiN [9], InOx [10] and NbN [3, 11]. The origin of the pseudogap phase in these materials is still not clear. Recent studies using scanning tunneling noise spectroscopy [12] show direct evidence of the existence of Cooper pairs well above the superconducting transition temperature, while presenting unusual normal-state electronic properties. This behaviour suggests that materials with low superfluid density are more susceptible to have the phase transition driven by phase fluctuations while keeping the pairing energy Δ finite [3].

Due to phase fluctuations, scanning tunneling spectroscopy measurements [9, 11] showed that the superconducting gap becomes inhomogeneous. When the phase is not ordered at all length scales, the characteristic zero resistivity of the superconducting state is lost. However, phase correlations can remain over finite lengths, segregating the superfluid into regions with higher or lower order parameter as well as into regions where the superconductivity is completely suppressed. This phenomena has been observed recently in FeTe_{0.55}Se_{0.45} [13] with a Josephson STM, which relies on measuring the superfluid density from the Josephson current through a superconducting tip with a similar Fermi energy and gap as that from the sample. Nevertheless, given the incapability of probing the superfluid reponse with scanning tunneling spectroscopy for a wider range of materials, we still lack of a broader picture that captures the relation between all the physics occurring in the pseudogap phase [3][14].

*The range of temperatures in which fluctuations in the order parameter are relevant in clean conventional superconductors was estimated by Ginzburg, $\Delta T/T_c \sim 10^{-12} - 10^{-14}$ [6].

[†]This phase is characterized by a depletion of the density of states of electrons in a region close to the Fermi energy.

1.3 Scanning tunneling microscopy as a probe for superfluid density

Before going in depth with the technical details of the measuring system, let us recall once more the goal of the project. We want to build a system that is sensitive to spatial changes in superfluid density without losing the other properties of a conventional STM measurement. For this, it is crucial to first clarify why typical STM cannot provide this information and why we do not want to resign from the conventional features of this method (sec.1.3.1).

1.3.1 Why STM?

Brief introduction to STM

As a brief summary of the mechanisms involved in STM, the basic principle consists of an atomically sharp tip close to the surface of the sample to study. Electrons tunnel through the vacuum, leading to a net current that depends on the distance between tip and sample as well as on the density of states (DOS) of both tip and sample [15]. In this way it is possible to determine for every scanning point the local DOS of the sample, which is proportional to the differential conductance, dI/dV [15].

To illustrate this idea, let us consider an ideal tunnelling spectroscopy measurement in a conventional superconductor with a normal-state tip, as shown in Fig. 1.1. When the sample is in the normal state (green curve), the relation between the tunneling current and the bias voltage (denoted by U in the figure) is linear, showing an energy independent density of states. On the other hand, when the sample is in the superconducting state, a gap Δ opens at the Fermi energy. This brings a depletion of the electronic density of states for scanning energies lower than the gap energy ($eU < \Delta$ in the figure), meaning that no current flows up to a bias energy of Δ . At $eU = \Delta$, the density of states diverges if $T = 0$ K which convoluted with the thermal broadening coming from finite temperatures ($T > 0$ K), leads to the *quasiparticle coherence peak*[‡], often related to the superconducting phase in unconventional superconductors [9, 11, 13]. Hence, from the scanning tunneling spectroscopy measurement it is possible to determine the SC pairing energy Δ , and the height of the coherence peaks.

[‡]Quasiparticle coherence peaks come from the Bogoliubov quasiparticle bands (E_k) which are related to the normal electron bands (ξ_k) as $E_k^2 = \Delta_k^2 + \xi_k^2$. These are elementary excitations above the condensate ground state and are formed by electron-hole superpositions, they are spin 1/2 particles. For more information see [5].

Figure 1.1: Sketch of ideal tunneling current and differential conductance (dI/dU) curves as function of the bias energy (eU) normalized with the gap energy (Δ) for a normal (green) and superconducting sample at $T = 0$ K (blue) and at a finite temperature (red). Figure adapted from [16].

Advantages of including STM

All the above-mentioned measurements are related to the real part of the complex conductivity of the sample (Sec. 1.3.4). The superfluid density, however, is related to the imaginary part of the complex conductivity of the sample (see Sec. 1.3.4). There are several spectroscopic techniques that are sensitive to the complex impedance, such as Broadband Corbino Spectroscopy [17, 18], that relies on reflection measurements through a coaxial line terminated by a flat sample. These techniques, however, do not contain the benefits of the STM probe, which not only include the possibility of scanning the surface of the sample but also determining the local electronic density of states with high accuracy.

For this, combining a method that measures the changes in the complex conductivity of the sample together with typical STM features provides unprecedented advantage to determine the local superfluid density and the electronic DOS at the same time for each point of the scan. In this thesis we show a possible way of incorporating a superfluid probe to the conventional STM mechanisms using RF reflectometry.

1.3.2 STM + RF reflectometry

To understand the principle of the superfluid density measurement method, let us first consider the basic idea of the setup, depicted in Fig. 1.2. This method combines typical STM together with microwave reflection measurements. Both DC and RF signals go through the tip and are analysed in different ports after being separated by the bias-tee.

The DC signal, is due to the tunnelling of electrons through the junction when applying a certain bias voltage to the sample. The RF signal comes from a microwave source, and after being reflected at the tip junction, goes back through the same electronic path to the RF output.

Figure 1.2: Simplified sketch of the set-up used for RF-reflection STM. There are two signals that go through the tip; RF and DC. The DC signal comes from bias voltage (V_B) -dependent tunneling current and is not affected by the impedance matching circuit. The RF signal comes from the RF source, goes to the tip and a fraction of it is reflected back to the source, where the ratio between sent and received signal is analysed. At the matching frequency, f_0 , the transmission is maximum and Z_L is transformed into Z_0 , see Fig. 1.3.

Figure 1.3: The impedance matching system is an intermediate circuit between the load and a transmission line of characteristic impedance Z_0 .

Microwave reflectometry consists on measuring the ratio between emitted and received signal, and it is given by the reflection coefficient Γ [§], whose magnitude lays between 0 and 1. This parameter is often measured as function of frequency, and can be described through Eq.1.1 as a relation between the impedance at the termination of the system, hence the load impedance (Z_L) and the characteristic impedance of the remaining electronics (Z_0). In this case, the load impedance is the impedance of the tip-sample system.

[§]In the scattering matrix formalism it is often referred to as S_{11} .

$$\Gamma(\omega) = \frac{Z_L(\omega) - Z_0}{Z_L(\omega) + Z_0}. \quad (1.1)$$

The reflection coefficient gives the impedance mismatch between the load and the characteristic impedance of the system. Typically, the impedance values of the tip-sample system (Z_L) differ significantly from the characteristic impedance of the rest of the set-up (which is usually $Z_0 = 50 \Omega$), and therefore, for most of the frequencies the value of Γ will be very close to 1. On the contrary, if the impedance of the tip-sample system lays close to Z_0 , the value of the reflection coefficient will drop to 0.

As a means to find a measurable signal, our approach consists on transforming the tip-sample impedance in a value close to Z_0 for one specific value of the frequency, the matching frequency f_0 . The reflection coefficient will only decrease for a small range of frequencies centered around f_0 leading to a resonance peak in the reflectometry signal (Fig.1.4). The resonance peak will carry the information about the sample under study, and hence will vary with the electronic properties of the sample. This is the key idea behind a method that is sensitive to changes in the sample impedance.

$$Z_L(\omega_0) \rightarrow Z_0$$

The transformation of the impedance of the tip-sample system at the matching frequency is acquired by an impedance matching circuit, depicted as the light green box in Fig.1.2. This is further discussed in Ch.2.

Figure 1.4: Calculated reflection coefficient as function of frequency for a load matched at $f_0 = 1$ GHz.

1.3.3 Tip-sample model

The load impedance Z_L refers to the lumped element electronic model of the tunnel junction, which is typically described as a resistor (R_T) and a capacitor (C_T) in parallel. R_T depends exponentially on the distance between tip and sample and it takes values in the range $100 \text{ M}\Omega - 1 \text{ G}\Omega$. The capacitance, C_T , comes from a combination between tip-sample and tip-ground capacitances, with values of the order of 100 fF and $1 - 10 \text{ pF}$, respectively.

In order to be sensitive to changes in the sample impedance, it is necessary to consider $h \ll D$, where h the distance between tip and sample and D the diameter of the tip, so that the impedance of an electric tip can be described as in Fig. 1.5. Here the complex surface sample impedance Z_s is in series with the tip-sample coupling capacitance C_c ,

Figure 1.5: Tip-sample model in the near-field regime with Z_s as the complex surface impedance of the sample, C_c the tip-sample coupling capacitance, C_s the stray capacitance and R_T the tunnel junction resistance.

whose value depends on the distance between tip and sample, but it typically takes values of the order of $1 - 100 \text{ fF}$. The stray capacitance, C_s , or the ‘non-end tip component’, depends on the ground shield and if tip and sample are very close, on the distance to the sample as well. R_T is the tunnel junction resistance, which for high enough frequencies ($\sim \text{GHz}$) has a very small contribution to the total impedance and hence it is negligible. This is known as the *near-field regime* [19]. Here the interaction between tip and sample can be seen as a cloud of electromagnetic field penetrating the sample, whose size is determined by the order of magnitude of the tip diameter. To create a true near field model, the size of D has to be small enough compared to the wavelength of the field as well as it has to fulfill the condition $|k_s|D \ll 1$, where $k_s = \omega(\epsilon_0\epsilon_s\mu_0\mu_s)^{1/2}$ is the wavenumber of the sample [19].

1.3.4 Two-fluid model

For a superconducting sample, it might be slightly counterintuitive to think that we can probe the superfluid response by measuring the sample impedance. Can these materials have a finite Z_s ?

In the presence of alternating electromagnetic fields (ac currents), the electric field that accelerates the supercurrent also affects the non-superconducting (or normal) electrons leading to energy dissipation in the material. This effect is well described by the *two-fluid model*, which approximates the behaviour of the normal and superconducting electrons to two ohmic conductive channels [5].

The model is based on Drude's conductivity

$$\sigma(\omega) = \frac{ne^2\tau/m}{1 - i\omega\tau}, \quad (1.2)$$

where n is the total electron density that can be divided into normal and superconducting components, $n = n_n + n_s$, with different relaxation times τ_n and τ_s . The superconducting relaxation time can be approximated as $\tau_s \sim \infty$, while typically for microwave frequencies $\omega\tau_n \ll 1$.

Therefore, the complex conductivity described by the model is

$$\sigma = \sigma' - i\sigma'' = \frac{n_n e^2 \tau_n}{m^*} - i \frac{n_s e^2}{m^* \omega}, \quad (1.3)$$

with m^* the quasiparticle mass. In Eq. 1.3, the real part corresponds to the fraction of conductivity carried by the normal electrons while the superconducting electrons carry the imaginary part, related to the susceptance of the material.

In the thin film limit ($d \ll \lambda_L$), the conductivity is related to the surface impedance, $\sigma d = Z_s^{-1}$, where $Z_s = R_s + i\omega L_s$. R_s is the surface resistance of the film while L_s is the surface inductance. In the near field regime, however, the properties of the sample are determined by the tip diameter, D , rather than by the thickness of the film. This is the characteristic size of the electromagnetic cloud that causes the interaction between tip and sample, due to the static character of the near-field [19].

At low temperatures, where the normal electron conductivity is much smaller than the imaginary part, $\sigma' \ll \sigma''$, the resistive and inductive parts take the following form [19, 20]:

$$R_s = \frac{\sigma'}{\sigma''^2 D}, \quad (1.4)$$

$$L_s = \frac{1}{\omega \sigma'' D}. \quad (1.5)$$

The energy dissipated in the system is proportional to R_s , which leads to the conclusion it scales with the frequency $\sim \omega^2$ and with the density of normal electrons, n_n , which are the ones that lead to the energy dissipation [5]. And therefore, the total complex impedance will be dominated by the reactive component, $Z_s \approx i\omega L_s$. Together with Eq. 1.3, the surface inductance derived from the two-fluid model in the near-field regime can be expressed as

$$L_s = \frac{m^*}{n_s e^2 D}. \quad (1.6)$$

The temperature dependence of the kinetic inductance is given by the magnetic penetration depth,

$$L_s = \mu_0 \frac{\lambda_L(T)^2}{D}. \quad (1.7)$$

where $\lambda_L(T) = \lambda_L(0)/\sqrt{1 - (T/T_c)^2}$.

The surface kinetic inductance will diverge at $T = T_c$ and will decrease for lower temperatures, as expected from $L_s \propto 1/n_s$ in Eq. 1.6. Above the critical temperature, in the case of BCS superconductors no kinetic inductance is expected, since the cooper pairs are broken and the gap closed. Hence, the sample impedance will be fully resistive ($Z_s = R_s$). This might not be the case for unconventional and strongly disordered superconductors, which are predicted to have an inhomogeneous order parameter above their critical temperature.

Why GHz?

The principal reason why high frequencies present a benefit to probe the superfluid density is given by the complex surface impedance of the sample, $Z_s = R_s + i\omega L_s$. Changes in the complex impedance due to variations in L_s are greatly enhanced at higher frequencies.

In addition, the tip-sample system in the *near-field regime* (sec.1.3.3), models the sample surface impedance in series with the tip-sample coupling capacitance,

$$Z_L^{-1} = \left(Z_s + \frac{1}{i\omega C_c} \right)^{-1} + i\omega C_s + \frac{1}{R_T} \quad (1.8)$$

For a reactive sample $Z_s \approx i\omega L$, at low frequencies the impedance of that branch of the circuit will be completely dominated by the coupling capacitance. Hence, to be sensitive enough to small changes in L , it is required to have $\omega^2 L C_c \sim 1$.

Apart from improving the sensitivity to changes in Z_s , high frequencies would also improve the temporal resolution of the STM and the signal-to-noise ratio[need ref here].

On the contrary, very high frequencies can also entail drawbacks. The first limiting factor at high frequencies is given by C_s , which dominates the total load impedance. The higher the frequency, the greater contribution from C_s . The second disadvantage is that

the electromagnetic radiation must not affect the superconducting order parameter. For this, we work in the regime where $hf \ll 2\Delta$, where at 1 GHz and for the pairing strength $\Delta \sim 0.1 - 10$ meV, the ratio is $hf/\Delta \sim 10^{-2} - 10^{-5}$.

1.3.5 Measurement method

The previous sections discuss the origin of the superconducting sample's surface impedance as well as the tip-sample load impedance-dependent reflection coefficient Γ . But how can we distinguish between having higher or lower superfluid density?

The key idea to probe the changes in superfluid density presented here consists on matching the tip-sample impedance, Z_L , to Z_0 at a chosen frequency f_0 . For this, it is essential to know the contributions from the components of the tip-sample system. The stray and coupling capacitances can be determined by fitting the measurements performed at different tip-sample distances in a well known material and the tunnel resistance can be determined from DC measurements. The sample's surface impedance is unknown, but the values in the superconducting regime at very low temperatures are estimated to be close to $Z_s \approx 0 \Omega$ [21]. Accordingly, Z_L can be matched at a negligible value of Z_s .

When scanning the sample, variations in Z_s may occur, while all the other parameters in Z_L stay constant (or their behaviour is known so that it is possible to subtract their contribution), i.e. variations in the coupling capacitance can be avoided if the sample is cleaved. An alteration in the superfluid density δn_s will lead to a change in the imaginary component of the sample impedance $\delta L_s \rightarrow \delta \Im[Z_s]$.

By changing the sample impedance δZ_s , Z_L will also vary in a smaller scale. If δZ_s is imaginary, then the variation δZ_L will be mostly imaginary[¶], whereas a real δZ_s only changes the real part of Z_L . The deviation in the imaginary component of the tip-sample impedance leads to a shift in the matching frequency, while a change in the real part lowers the quality factor of the resonance peak at the matching frequency, as illustrated in Fig. 1.6. The system is matched at $f_0 = 2$ GHz with $C_c = 100$ fF, $C_s = 2$ pF, $R_T = 1$ G Ω and $Z_s = 0 \Omega$ (blue curve). When increasing $R_s = 10^{-3} \Omega$, the resonance peak dampens considerably (green curve), while $Z_s = i\omega_0 L_s = 0.035i \Omega$ shifts the resonance frequency (orange curve).

It is not trivial to see where do the matching frequency changes due to δZ_s come from, since the mechanisms used to match the impedance are yet to be discussed. However, we can already make some predictions following the idea behind [20], where they calculate the change in the kinetic inductance of TiN transmission line microresonators from the shift in the resonance frequency when varying the temperature. This method is quantitatively

[¶]The real component of Z_L will also change if δZ_s is imaginary but in a much smaller scale. If $\delta Z_s = i\Omega$, $\frac{Re[\delta Z_L]}{Im[\delta Z_L]} \sim 10^{-6} - 10^{-7}$.

Figure 1.6: Numerical calculation of the reflection coefficient as function of frequency for $f_0 = 2$ GHz, $C_c = 100$ fF, $C_s = 2$ pF and $R_T = 1$ G Ω . The blue curve is the impedance matched case where $Z_s = 0$ Ω and while still matched at that value, changing the imaginary component $Z_s = 0.035i$ Ω shifts the resonance peak by $\delta f = 2000$ Hz (orange). Increasing the real part of the impedance, $Z_s = 10^{-3}$ Ω , dampens the resonance frequency (green).

very different to what we propose in this work, yet it has some qualitative similarities: they have the sharpest peak from the reflection measurement at the lowest temperature, and hence when L_s is very small, while for our case, we have impedance matching at the lowest L_s . When they increase the temperature below T_c , due to Cooper pair breaking excitations, the superfluid density is expected to decrease. This enhances the value of L_s and the resonance peak shifts to a lower frequency. For our system, the expected relation between superfluid density and frequency shift is therefore similar as in [20],

$$\frac{\delta n_s}{n_{s0}} \propto -\frac{\delta L_s}{L_{s0}} \propto \frac{\delta f_0}{f_0}, \quad (1.9)$$

where n_{s0} and L_{s0} are the values at f_0 . Hence, the temperature and spatial dependence of the shift in the resonance frequency is a direct probe of the deviations on the superfluid density.

Impedance matching circuits

This chapter discusses impedance matching circuits for STM tunnel junctions at microwave frequencies. The main idea here is depicted in Fig.2.1 where an impedance matching circuit is placed between the load and a transmission line. This system transforms the load impedance into a desired value of typically $Z_0 = 50\Omega$ at a given matching frequency, f_0 . In other words, the impedance seen at the matching frequency when looking at the circuit is Z_0 .

Figure 2.1: The impedance matching system is an intermediate circuit between the load and a transmission line of characteristic impedance Z_0 .

The utility of this intermediate circuit comes from the reflection coefficient, S_{11} , as described in eq.1.1. At the matching frequency, the load impedance is transformed to Z_0 and the reflection coefficient is minimum, while the power transfer is maximum. For other frequencies, the reflection coefficient will be higher due to the difference between the impedance of the load, Z_L , and that of the rest of the system. Therefore, S_{11} will be maximum for most frequencies with the exception of the minimum at the matching frequency f_0 and a bandwidth around that value.

In principle, it is possible to match any desired complex load impedance as long as the real part is positive. In practice, however, different circuits represent different challenges

and some of them might not be suitable for a specific range of frequencies.

The following sections encompass a brief introduction to the two main types of impedance matching circuits - with lumped elements and with distributed elements - followed by a more extensive study of coplanar waveguides with special focus on the losses.

2.1 Lumped elements

Lumped element matching circuits are mainly formed by inductors and capacitors. The name refers to a circuit composed by elements that have a small size compared to the electrical wavelength, thus the variations in current and voltage. The simplest type of matching network, the *L-section*, is composed by a susceptance, B , in parallel and a reactance, X , in series as depicted in figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: *L-section lumped-element matching circuits for (a) $R_L > Z_0$ and (b) $R_L < Z_0$. From [22]*

The circuit in figure 2.2a matches a load $Z_L = R_L + jX_L$ where $R_L > Z_0$, while the circuit in Fig. 2.2b is used to match the case $R_L < Z_0$. Since we want to match a complex load, it is necessary to have two degrees of freedom in the matching circuit, namely B and X , to transform the real part to Z_0 and the imaginary part to zero.

The STM tip-sample system as described in section 1.3.3 would lead to a load impedance of $Z_L \approx 10^{-5} - 76j \Omega$ in the case of a negligible sample contribution, $Z_s \sim 0 \Omega$, a tunnel resistance $R_T = 1 \text{ G}\Omega$, with the parallel capacitances $C_c = 0.1 \text{ pF}$ and $C_s = 2 \text{ pF}$ at a resonance frequency $f_0 = 1 \text{ GHz}$. For this reason, only the second circuit would lead to a matching of the load impedance at this frequency. The analytical solutions are derived in Pozar [22]:

From the condition to match the impedance in the case depicted in Fig. 2.2b,

$$Z_0 = jB + \frac{1}{R_L + j(X_L + X)}, \quad (2.1)$$

the solutions for X and B

$$X = \pm \sqrt{R_L(Z_0 - R_L)} - X_L, \quad (2.2)$$

$$B = \pm \frac{\sqrt{(Z_0 - R_L)/R_L}}{Z_0}, \quad (2.3)$$

where the upper and lower signs refer to the same solution.

The equations for the load described above give the following values: $B_1 = 59.01 \Omega^{-1}$, $X_1 = 75.81 \Omega$ and $B_2 = -59.01 \Omega^{-1}$, $X_2 = 75.77 \Omega$. Both solutions give exactly the same reflection feature. If X is positive, it describes the impedance of an inductor $X = \omega L$ while if it is negative $X = -1/\omega C$. Positive B indicates we have a capacitor $B = \omega C$ whereas for a negative value $B = -1/\omega L$. The values that come out of the calculation are very precise and it can be extremely difficult to fabricate such exact inductance and capacitances. Hence, for the first case we would have an inductor in series and a capacitor in parallel ($L_{X1} = 12.1$ nH and $C_{B1} = 9.391$ nF) while for the second case both elements are inductors ($L_{X2} = 12.1$ nH and $L_{B2} = 2.7$ pH). The fact that we use less exact capacitance (\sim nF) and inductances (\sim 0.1 nH) will produce a frequency shift with respect to the resonance frequency of $\delta f = 1.458$ MHz, but no notable change in the Q factor. A commercial inductor of \sim 12 nH has a typical tolerance of 2% [23], which leads to a frequency shift of $\delta f \sim 10$ MHz at $f_0 = 1$ GHz, while a capacitor of \sim 9 nF usually has a tolerance of 10%, shifting the frequency about 10 kHz.

Figure 2.3: Reflection coefficient as function of frequency for different sample impedances. Variations in the real part of the sample impedance change lower the quality factor of the signal, while variations in the imaginary part will shift the resonance peak.

Figure 2.3 presents the reflection coefficient as function of frequency for different sample impedances, Z_s , with the values indicated above. The circuit is matched for a very small Z_s (blue curve) at $f_0 = 998.542$ MHz due to the approximation of the inductor and capacitor values L_{X1} and C_{B1} . We clearly see how the kinetic inductance of the sample shifts the resonance frequency $\delta f = 7458$ Hz.

A realistic inductor can be modelled with a resistor in series and a capacitor in parallel that represents the parasitic capacitance due to the wires of the coil. This parasitic capacitance together with the inductance resonates at the self-resonance frequency. At much lower frequencies than the self-resonance frequency (SRF), the inductor has barely a constant inductance. When the frequency approaches the SRF, the inductance drops until reaching zero at the SRF. For frequencies higher than this, the inductor is completely dominated by the parasitic capacitances. The self-resonance frequency for an inductor with nH inductance may typically be in the range 1 – 10 GHz. Assuming we are measuring in the optimum frequency range, and hence neglecting the parasitic capacitances, figure 2.4 shows the effect of the resistance of the inductor on the reflection coefficient. The typical values for the resistance are in the order of Ω , and therefore, would completely dampen the resonance signal.

Figure 2.4: Reflection coefficient as function of frequency for different values of α .

One possible solution would be to use inductors made out of superconductors to reduce the resistive losses. Another possibility would be to take into account the losses of the inductor in Eq. 2.2 and Eq.2.3 in series with the load resistance. In this way, the inductance and the capacitance to match the impedance would vary slightly. However, even if theoretically this idea works, in practice the resistance and parasitic capacitances

would also vary with the inductance. This makes it difficult to fabricate inductors with on-demand resistive and capacitive properties.

Besides the circuits mentioned above, which only have the matching frequency as a degree of freedom for a given load impedance, there is another type of lumped-element circuit, the π -section. This idea is developed in [24] where, in order to have more tuning parameters, they add a third component to the circuit; a capacitor in parallel with the load impedance. In our case, for the STM tip-sample model where

Figure 2.5: Effect of adding extra capacitance parallel to the tunnel junction on the reflection coefficient resonance signal as function of frequency. Blue curve represents a negligible sample impedance while the orange curve shows the shift in the resonance frequency when the sample has imaginary impedance. The values of the frequency shift are presented in table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Frequency shift (δf) of the reflection coefficient minima between the matched impedance at $Z_s = 0 \Omega$ and $Z_s = j0.5$ represented in figure 2.5 with blue and orange curves, respectively for three different stray capacitances (C_s). The frequency step of the calculation is different for each case.

C_s (pF)	2	10	20
δf (Hz)	7458.72	1560.67	757.81
Step (Hz)	0.04	0.01	0.003

we already have a capacitor in parallel with the tunnel junction resistance, this extra capacitance would just add the value to the stray capacitance of the junction, making it greater. If $C_s = 2$ pF and we add a parallel capacitor of $C_{extra} = 1$ pF, then this would behave the same way as if we had $C'_s = 3$ pF. Furthermore, increasing the value of the stray capacitance lessens the sensitivity to changes in the sample, since this branch of

the circuit would dominate the total impedance. To illustrate this idea, Fig. 2.5 shows the reflection coefficient as function of frequency for three different values of the stray capacitance: $C_s = 2, 10$ and 20 pF. The orange and blue curves indicate different sample impedance, $Z_s = 0 \Omega$ (blue) and $Z_s = j0.5 \Omega$ (orange) and the shift in the resonance frequency due to the change in the sample reactance for each of the three cases is shown in Tab. 2.1. Greater capacitances parallel to the junction resistance decrease the sensitivity to changes in the sample reactance.

2.1.1 Disadvantages of lumped elements

At high frequencies, usually in the order of GHz, the lumped elements present a problem that is difficult to avoid: parasitic effects in the circuit play a significant role [24]. For this reason, it is convenient to consider impedance matching circuits with distributed elements, such as transmission lines. These type of circuits are described in section 2.2.2, preceded by a brief introduction to transmission line theory.

2.2 Transmission lines

Before discussing impedance matching with transmission lines, it is necessary to briefly describe the principal expressions that characterise them. This introduction is based on the work by D. Pozar [22].

Figure 2.6: Lumped element model for an infinitesimal length of a transmission line.

In contrast with lumped elements, transmission lines are distributed elements formed by at least two conductors - to transport transversal electromagnetic (TEM) modes -. A uniform cross sectional geometry provides constant impedance throughout their length, which yields to a guided wave propagation with minimum reflections. For gigahertz frequencies, their size is comparable to the wavelength, which makes an overall lumped

element description of the transmission line highly inaccurate, since the voltage and current vary in magnitude and phase over that length. Instead, a piece of transmission line of infinitesimal length can be modelled as a lumped element circuit, as shown in Fig. 2.6. R , L , G and C are quantities defined per unit length described below.

- R is the series resistance of both conductors due to conductor losses, Ω/m .
- L is the series inductance coming from the conductors, H/m .
- G is the shunt conductance from losses in the dielectric, S/m .
- C is the shunt capacitance between the conductors, F/m .

2.2.1 Wave propagation along a transmission line

Transmission lines are extensively used to guide radio frequency alternating currents. We describe the behaviour of these waves in the line with special emphasis on the reflection coefficient originated from an impedance mismatch within the line or at the end of it.

Applying Kirtchhoff's current and voltage laws, taking $\Delta x \rightarrow 0$ and considering phasors of the form $\tilde{V}(x, t) = \text{Re}\{V(x)e^{i\omega t}\}$ and $\tilde{I}(x, t) = \text{Re}\{I(x)e^{i\omega t}\}$, we get to the following general solutions[pozar],

$$V(x) = V_0^+ e^{-\gamma x} + V_0^- e^{\gamma x} \quad (2.4)$$

$$I(x) = \frac{V_0^+}{Z_0} e^{-\gamma x} - \frac{V_0^-}{Z_0} e^{\gamma x} \quad (2.5)$$

where γ is the propagation constant,

$$\gamma = \alpha + j\beta = \sqrt{(R + j\omega L)(G + j\omega C)}. \quad (2.6)$$

The '+' or '-' signs in Eq. 2.4 and 2.5 indicate the propagation direction of the wave* and Z_0 is the characteristic impedance of the transmission line,

$$Z_0 = \sqrt{\frac{R + j\omega L}{G + j\omega C}}. \quad (2.7)$$

The real part of the propagation constant, α , is the attenuation constant that causes the damping of the amplitude of the wave. β is the phase constant and it is related to the wavelength in the following way:

$$\lambda = \frac{2\pi}{\beta}, \quad (2.8)$$

*We consider that $e^{-\gamma x}$ (V^+) represents the incident wave while $e^{\gamma x}$ (V^-) describes the reflected waves.

and the phase velocity,

$$v_p = \frac{\omega}{\beta} = \lambda f. \quad (2.9)$$

If we consider a transmission line terminated in an arbitrary load impedance Z_L (Fig. 2.7), the incident wave will be reflected due to the impedance mismatch between Z_0 and Z_L at $x = 0$. The reflection coefficient at the load Γ_L ,

$$\Gamma_L = \frac{V_0^-}{V_0^+} = \frac{Z_L - Z_0}{Z_L + Z_0}, \quad (2.10)$$

will take values in the range $[-1, 1]$ depending on the value of Z_L . If the circuit is open, $Z_L = \infty$, then $\Gamma_L = 1$ will be maximum and if it is shorted, $Z_L = 0$ and $\Gamma_L = -1$. Usually, the reflection coefficient is measured in absolute values, which gives a minimum signal (no reflection) at the matched impedance $Z_L = Z_0$.

The load impedance can also be expressed in terms of the reflection coefficient,

$$Z_L = \frac{1 + \Gamma_L}{1 - \Gamma_L}. \quad (2.11)$$

Figure 2.7: Loaded transmission line of length d .

In the same way that the signal travels throughout the transmission line with a complex exponential position dependence (Eq. 2.4 and Eq.2.5), the reflection coefficient will vary with position. If we consider the system depicted in Fig. 2.7, and we want to determine the reflection coefficient at $x = -d$ from the load, we take the ratio between the propagating waves at that position,

$$\Gamma_{in}(-d) = \frac{V_0^- e^{\gamma(-d)}}{V_0^+ e^{-\gamma(-d)}} = \Gamma_L e^{-2\gamma d} = \Gamma_L e^{-2\alpha d} e^{-2j\beta d}. \quad (2.12)$$

An equivalent approach to the position dependent reflection coefficient is to consider a position dependent load impedance. The idea behind this is based on the way the transmission line sees the load, which depends once more on the position within the

transmission line. The effective value of the load impedance at position $x = -d$ takes the form

$$Z_{in}(-d) = \frac{V_0^+ [e^{\gamma d} + \Gamma_L e^{-\gamma d}]}{\frac{V_0^+}{Z_0} [e^{\gamma d} - \Gamma_L e^{-\gamma d}]} = Z_0 \frac{Z_L + Z_0 \tanh \gamma d}{Z_0 + Z_L \tanh \gamma d}. \quad (2.13)$$

2.2.2 Stub tuner

A very typical impedance matching circuit with distributed elements consists of an open or short ended stub connected in series or in parallel to the main transmission feed line at a distance d from the load. An example of the shunt stub tuner is shown in figure Fig. 2.8a. The tuning parameters in this system are the distance from the stub to the load and the reactance given by the stub (Y_{stub}), which can be tuned either by changing the length, the geometry or the characteristic impedance of the transmission line.

For the shunt stub case, it is convenient to work with admittances, $Y = 1/Z$. The length d is chosen in a way such that the admittance Y_1 after the first stub has the form $Y_0 + jB$. Therefore, the length of the shunt stub l can be tuned so that the susceptance is chosen to be $-jB$ and match the load, $Y_0 = 1/Z_0$.

Figure 2.8: Single (a) and double (b) stub tuner impedance matching circuits. The shunt stubs are either open or short-circuited.

In addition to the single stub tuner, there is the *double stub tuner*, which consists of two stubs connected in parallel to the feed line at a fixed distance from each other, d , and the feed line terminated with the load. This idea is depicted in Fig. 2.8b. The main advantage of the double stub tuner is that tuning the circuit to match at a different frequency or with a different load becomes a much easier task than with the single stub. This is because the distance between the stubs and to the load can be fixed, whilst the reactances of the two shunt stubs, Y_{stub1} and Y_{stub2} , can be easily varied by changing either the length of the lines, the geometry or the termination impedance. For this reason, this is the impedance matching circuit we will refer to from this point on. For fixed circuits

such as printed circuit boards or printed chips, the most convenient way of tuning the reactances of the stubs is by changing the termination impedance, since it can be easily implemented with a varactor diode [25] or a SQUID [26] at the end of each shunt line.

In a more realistic situation, the load would be at an arbitrary distance from the first stub, which can be equivalently considered as a transformed load impedance next to stub 1, that can be recalculated using Eq.2.13. Here we will consider Z_L as the transformed load impedance after a line of known length.

Assuming that the geometry of the transmission lines is such that the characteristic impedance is constant Z_0 throughout the line, we can determine the lengths of the lossless shunt stubs by calculating the imaginary part of their admittances B_{stub1} and B_{stub2} to get an impedance match at frequency f_0 . Here we will consider that the shunt stubs are terminated with an open-circuited load. The only condition for matching Z_L with two shunt stubs separated by a distance d comes from the real part of the admittance, G_L , that has to fulfill the following condition

$$0 \leq G_L \leq \frac{Y_0}{\sin^2 \beta d}, \quad (2.14)$$

where $\beta = 2\pi f/v_p$. Hence, not all distances d ensure a matched load at certain frequency. After fixing d , the susceptance at the first and second stubs is

$$B_{stub1} = -B_L \frac{Y_0 \pm \sqrt{(1+t^2)G_L Y_0 - G_L^2 t^2}}{t} \quad (2.15)$$

$$B_{stub2} = \frac{\pm Y_0 \sqrt{Y_0 G_L (1+t^2) - G_L^2 t^2} + G_L Y_0}{G_L t}, \quad (2.16)$$

with $t = \tan \beta d$. The upper and lower signs correspond to the same solutions. The lengths of the open-circuited shunt stubs,

$$l_i^{open} = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi} \arctan \left(\frac{B_i}{Y_0} \right) \quad (2.17)$$

where $i = stub1, stub2$.

Since the length of the stubs is proportional to $\arctan(x)$, the choice of lengths is not unique; the stub tuner will match the impedance at lengths indicated by Eq. 2.17 but adding $\lambda/2$ an arbitrary number of times to such lengths will not change the result. This is useful to keep in mind when fabricating the stub tuner.

2.2.3 Matching in a lossless case

Before going further in detail with the stub tuner circuit, we shall consider an ideal lossless case.

The stub tuner depicted in figure 2.9 shows a load impedance Z_L that follows the tip-sample system described in section 1.3.3 with $C_s = 2$ pF and $C_c = 100$ fF and a sample impedance close to zero ($Z_s = 10^{-9} + j10^{-20}$ Ω , precisely) matched at the resonance frequency $f_0 = 2$ GHz. The shunt stubs are distance $d = \lambda/8 = 8.063$ mm apart and the calculated lengths of the stubs that match the total load are $l_1 = 29.079$ mm and $l_2 = 16.123$ mm with μm precision.

Figure 2.9: Double stub tuner that matches the load impedance Z_L described in the text at $f_0 = 2$ GHz.

Fig. 2.10 shows the reflection coefficient around the resonance frequency $f = 2$ GHz for different values of the sample impedance without approximating the stub lengths to μm , hence with the full length calculated from Eq. 2.17. The increase of the kinetic inductance (or the sample reactance) clearly shifts the resonance peak to a lower resonance frequency (see Tab. 2.2). The real contribution of the sample impedance, only lowers the quality factor with no shift in the resonance frequency.

Z_s (Ω)	$\sim 0 + 0j$ (matched)	$0.005 + 0j$	$0.4j$	$0.9j$
δf_0 (Hz)	0.0	0.0	8066	12595
Q	149 644 442	15 219 990	133 199 539	172 175 165

Table 2.2: Change in resonance frequency, δf_0 , and quality factor, Q , of the reflection coefficient resonance peak for different sample impedances Z_s (shown in Fig. 2.10).

Figure 2.11 compares the reflection coefficients of a system that has the stub lengths rounded with a precision of μm with a system that as the exact value obtained from Eq. 2.17. This is a closer scenario to what we will deal with experimentally, and hence necessary to consider. The approximation of the lengths can shift up or down the resonance frequency, but when the impedance of the sample varies, the system will mirror the behaviour shown in Fig. 2.10 and the frequency shift due to the sample properties will be exactly the same, $\delta f = 8066.08$ Hz for $L_k = 0.2$ nH.

Figure 2.10: Reflection coefficient as function of frequency after impedance matching with a double stub tuner for different sample impedances Z_s . The lengths of the stubs are directly obtained from Eq. 2.15 and 2.16.

Figure 2.11: Reflection coefficient as function of frequency after impedance matching with a double stub tuner for different sample impedances Z_s . Blue curve centered at $f_0 = 2$ GHz has the same parameters as in 2.10 while for the other curves the lengths of the stubs are approximated to μm precision.

All the calculations depicted before show an ideal case of a lossless matching circuit. In the next section, we will study how this scenario changes when considering a non-zero attenuation constant.

2.2.4 The effect of losses

The main source of losses in a transmission line comes from the finite resistance of the conductor (R) and the finite conductance of the dielectric (G). These losses are comprised in the attenuation constant α of the transmission line and vary with the geometry per unit of length and the materials used. The general expression for α in small-loss approximation ($RG/\omega^2LC \ll 1$) is given by Eq. 2.18,

$$\alpha = \text{Re}[\gamma] \approx \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{R}{Z_0} + GZ_0 \right). \quad (2.18)$$

If we consider a lossy medium with a α constant in frequency[†], for the values mentioned in sec. 2.2.3, we can see which is the dependence of the reflection coefficient with the losses as shown in Fig. 2.12. The Q factors of the signal for each α are given in Tab. 2.3.

Figure 2.12: Γ as function of the frequency for different values of α . The parameters used for the calculation are given in sec. 2.2.3 considering the full lengths of the stubs.

α (Np/m)	0 (matched)	10^{-10}	10^{-8}	10^{-6}
Q	184 355 400	184 284 055	176 323 126	47 771 869

Table 2.3: Change in quality factor, Q , of the reflection coefficient for different attenuation constants, α (shown in Fig.2.12).

The attenuation constant is an important factor to consider when doing impedance matching. A typical value of α for a transmission line made of copper on teflon substrate

[†]This is an ideal case, α always depends on frequency [27]

[28] is $\alpha = 5.15$ dB/m (0.5929Np/m). This is far above the limit to see a measurable signal in our stub tuner system if we compare it with the values shown in Fig.2.12. Moreover, as long as we know the value of the losses coming from the geometry, conductor and dielectric, we can tune the lengths of the stubs in such a way that we overcome the effect of the losses. Since it is not possible to solve Eq. 2.17 analytically for $\alpha \neq 0$, we use a numerical calculation to change the lengths slightly and in this way have back the reflection coefficient at the desired resonance frequency.

Figure 2.13: Reflection coefficient, Γ , as function of the extra lengths of the stubs, δL_1 and δL_2 . The origin of the graphs corresponds to the lengths given in sec.2.2.3 approximated to μm as well as the parameters used for the calculation. The attenuation constant is $\alpha = 0.5929$ Np/m. The values of the extra lengths at minimum Γ in [a] are $\delta L_1 = 3.33$ mm and $\delta L_2 = -1.467$ mm. The values are not unique, the minimum of Γ is a periodic function of the stub lengths [b].

Fig. 2.13 shows the reflection coefficient as function of the extra length of the stubs added to $l_1 = 29.079$ mm and $l_2 = 16.123$ mm at a fixed frequency of $f_0 = 2$ GHz for $\alpha = 0.5929$ Np/m. The minimum of the reflection coefficient is found at $l_1 + \delta l_1 = 26.577$ mm and $l_2 + \delta l_2 = 17.911$ mm (Fig. 2.13a). The choice of lengths, as we can see in Fig. 2.13b, is not unique. This is related to the periodicity of Eq. 2.17.

It is possible to have the minimum of the reflection coefficient back by changing slightly the lengths of the stubs after considering the losses, yet the quality factor of the stub tuner will inevitably decrease, as shown in Fig.2.14. This will reduce the resolution we have with respect to changes in the load (Q_L), since the total quality factor of the system can only be dominated by the load if the quality factor of the impedance matching circuit is $Q_{IM} \gg Q_L$ [29]. The internal quality factor of a transmission line is given by

$$Q_{in} = \frac{\beta}{2\alpha}. \quad (2.19)$$

Reducing the attenuation constant, therefore, will increase the quality factor of the

transmission line. This can be achieved through a superconducting transmission line, where the attenuation constant has been determined to be around $\alpha \sim 0.001$ Np/m [30, 31].

Figure 2.14: Reflection coefficient as function of frequency with the parameters from sec. 2.2.3 and lengths approximated to μm for $\alpha = 0$ Np/m (blue) vs. $\alpha = 0.5929$ Np/m (orange) and different sample impedances.

Frequency shift with losses

Fig. 2.15 shows the change in the reflection signal as function of the sample impedance for $\alpha = 0.5929$ Np/m. Following the same procedure as in section 2.2.3, the system is matched for $Z_s \approx 0 \Omega$ at 2 GHz. The reason why the resonance frequency is shifted upwards for the matched sample impedance (blue curve) is due to approximating the lengths of the stubs to μm .

Z_s (Ω)	$\sim 0 + 0j$ (matched)	0.5	$0.9j$
δf_0 (Hz)	0.0	0.0	15318
Q	136.37	136.18	136.35

Table 2.4: Change in resonance frequency δf_0 and quality factor, Q , of the reflection coefficient for different sample impedances when the system is matched with an attenuation constant $\alpha = 0.5929$ Np/m (shown in Fig.2.15).

Figure 2.15: Reflection coefficient as function of frequency with the parameters from sec. 2.2.3 and lengths approximated to μm for different sample impedances, $Z_s = 0 \Omega$ (blue), 0.5Ω (orange) and $j0.9 \Omega$ (green).

Minimizing the effect of losses

Even though the materials used for the matching circuit are well-known, determining the losses with precision will still be a difficult task. For this reason, we will consider a system where 1) the losses are as minimum as possible to provide a better resolution for the load impedance and 2) the reactances of the stubs are tunable. For the first aim we use superconducting coplanar transmission lines made of NbTiN on undoped Si, which provide considerably smaller losses compared to non-superconducting lines (~ 100 times smaller) [28, 31]. The theory of coplanar transmission lines is discussed in section 2.3. The calculations to implement the stubs with tunable reactances are in section 2.4.

2.3 Superconducting Coplanar Transmission Lines

Coplanar transmission lines consist on a conducting strip with width ‘ s ’ separated from the ground plane on both sides by a gap of width ‘ w ’, as shown in fig. 2.16. The conductors of thickness ‘ t ’ lay on the insulating substrate of thickness ‘ h ’ and dielectric constant ϵ_r . These transmission lines give the possibility of choosing the width of the center strip independently from the dielectric thickness [25].

Figure 2.16: Sketch of the geometry of a coplanar transmission line per unit of length. The center conductor carries the RF signal while the side-conductors are the ground.

In this section we first study the general expressions that characterize CTLs from the lumped element inductance L and capacitance C for a perfect conductor using derivations from conformal mapping technique described by R. N. Simons [27]. To consider the effect of superconductivity in the transmission line, we consider the extra inductive term L_k [32] (see section 2.3.1).

The geometry per unit length of the transmission line and properties of the substrate can fully determine the characteristic impedance Z_0 , the phase constant β and the attenuation constant α . Assuming that $t \ll s \ll h$, we can neglect the thicknesses of the conductor and the dielectric in the calculations. The effective dielectric constant is given by the following expression,

$$\epsilon_{eff} = 1 + \frac{1 - \epsilon_r}{2} \frac{K(k_1)K(k'_0)}{K(k_0)K(k'_1)} \approx \frac{1 + \epsilon_r}{2}. \quad (2.20)$$

where K are the elliptic integrals of the first kind, with arguments

$$k_0 = \frac{s}{s + 2w}, \quad (2.21)$$

$$k_1 = \frac{\sinh \pi s / 4h}{\sinh \pi (s + 2w) / 4h}, \quad (2.22)$$

$$k'_i = \sqrt{1 - k_i^2}, \quad i = 0, 1. \quad (2.23)$$

The lumped element inductance and capacitance are derived from conformal mapping technique [27, 32],

$$L = \mu_0 \frac{K(k_0)}{4K(k'_0)} \quad (2.24)$$

$$C = \frac{1 + \epsilon_r}{2} \frac{4K(k'_0)}{K(k_0)}. \quad (2.25)$$

And therefore, the expressions that determine Z_0 and β ,

$$Z_0 = \sqrt{\frac{L}{C}} = \frac{30\pi}{\sqrt{\epsilon_{eff}}} \frac{K(k'_0)}{K(k_0)}, \quad (2.26)$$

$$\beta = 2\pi f \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon_{eff}}}{c}. \quad (2.27)$$

Dielectric losses

The attenuation constant depends on the losses from both the substrate and the conductor. Since we use a superconductor, we will initially assume that the conductor has no losses[‡] and therefore, the attenuation constant will be fully determined by the dielectric losses given in [27],

$$\alpha_d = \frac{\pi \epsilon_r f \tan \delta (\epsilon_{eff} - 1)}{\sqrt{\epsilon_{eff}} c (\epsilon_r - 1)} \quad (2.28)$$

Here $\tan \delta$ is the loss tangent of the dielectric, with skin depth δ

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{\pi f \mu_r \mu_0}}, \quad (2.29)$$

where ρ is the resistivity of the substrate, f the signal frequency and μ_r and μ_0 the relative permeability of the dielectric and permeability of the vacuum, respectively.

Radiation losses

There is yet a third type of loss source: losses due to self radiation. There are two known mechanisms for radiation losses [33]. The first one is due to surface waves at frequencies well above 100 GHz. Our operation frequency range can go up to a maximum of 3 GHz, hence surface waves do not affect our measurements. The second mechanism is a result of different propagation speed in the conductor and in the substrate. This becomes relevant at substrate thicknesses comparable to the signal wavelength λ . The thickness of the substrate used for the calculations is 500 μm , while the wavelength is of the order of ~ 5 cm. Therefore, it will not influence our system.

Other propagation modes

The geometry of the CTL has to be such that the characteristic impedance is $Z_0 = 50 \Omega$ and that we avoid propagation modes other than the first coplanar waveguide mode. There are three ways in which the structure may propagate [34]: coplanar waveguide mode, microstrip mode and coupled slotlines mode. Microstrip modes are prevented if

[‡]At finite temperatures there will be losses in the superconductor coming from the quasiparticle excitations (see sec. 2.3.1).

$h \gg s + 2w$, while slotlines are avoided with jumpers connecting the ground at both sides of the strip line. To prevent the propagation of higher modes, we choose $s + 2w < \lambda/2$.

2.3.1 Kinetic inductance and AC losses

In a perfect conductor, the magnetic field is completely shielded by the free charges from the conductor and therefore the inductance is uniquely related to the energy stored outside of the material, referred to as the geometric inductance, L_m . This is the inductance used in the previous section. In a superconductor, however, the magnetic field can enter a distance determined by the penetration depth, λ_L . This adds a contribution to the total inductance, the kinetic inductance L_k , that comes from the kinetic energy of the Cooper pairs flowing in this magnetically penetrated layer.

$$L_k = \mu_0 \frac{\lambda_L(T)^2}{ts} g(s, w, t), \quad (2.30)$$

$$\lambda_L(T) = \frac{\lambda_L(0)}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{T}{T_c}\right)^4}}. \quad (2.31)$$

Since $t < \lambda_L$, the magnetic field will penetrate the entire superconducting layer. However if $t > 2\lambda_L$, t should be replaced by $2\lambda_L$. Here $\lambda_L(0)$ is the London penetration depth at 0 K and $g(s, w, t)$ the geometric factor, derived in [35] as

$$g(s, w, d) = \frac{1}{2k_0^2 K(k_0)^2} \left(-\ln \frac{t}{4s} - \frac{s}{s+2w} \ln \frac{t}{4(s+2w)} + \frac{2(w+s)}{s+2w} \ln \frac{w}{s+w} \right) \quad (2.32)$$

The magnetic inductance does not depend on the type of material, but on the geometry, which gives us the freedom to choose a material that has a lower kinetic inductance compared to the geometric value and most important, that is somewhat stable with small changes in temperature.

To this end, we study the kinetic inductance of three different superconductors: Nb, NbTiN and MoGe with critical temperatures of 9.2 K, 16.2 K and 7.25 K, and approximate penetration depths 400 Å, 260 nm and 500 nm, respectively [36–39].

Figure 2.17: Geometric inductance for $s = 24 \mu\text{m}$, $w = 13 \mu\text{m}$ and $h = 500 \mu\text{m}$ (purple dotted) and kinetic inductances for Nb (green solid line), NbTiN (blue line) and MoGe (red curve).

Figure 2.17 shows the magnetic and kinetic inductances of Nb, NbTiN and MoGe as function of the temperature. The geometry of the line has the following parameters: $s = 24 \mu\text{m}$ and $w = 13 \mu\text{m}$ with $t = 150 \text{ nm}$ and $h = 500 \mu\text{m}$.

Unlike for Nb, NbTiN has a thickness dependent kinetic inductance (Eq. 2.30), but due to the contribution from the geometric factor, this dependence is not intuitive. Fig. 2.18 shows the kinetic and geometric inductances as function of the thickness of the NbTiN film. The thickness still needs to be much smaller than the parameters that define the geometry of the transmission line, to avoid higher order propagating modes. However, it is important to consider a thick enough superconducting layer that minimizes the contribution from the kinetic inductance.

The characteristic impedance here is defined as $Z_0 = \sqrt{L/C}$ and the phase constant $\beta = \omega\sqrt{LC}$, with $L = L_m + L_k$. Therefore, it is fundamental to keep the kinetic inductance small to avoid temperature dependence in Z_0 and β . Even if Nb is the material that has the lowest kinetic inductance ($\sim 5 \text{ nH}$), we chose our matching circuit to be made of NbTiN for two principal reasons:

1) First, Nb has a well-defined crystal structure very difficult to reproduce by sputtering technique. Impurities and lattice imperfections play an important role. This makes Nb films to have typically more deteriorated properties when they are thin enough ($\sim 100 \text{ nm}$), while NbTiN is a disordered material and hence, easier to reproduce.

2) The more amorphous the material, the smaller its quasiparticle scattering time, τ . From Eq. 2.33 we can see the dependence of τ on the resistive losses of the SCPW derived from the two fluid model [20, 40]. This leads us to the second reason; due to the

Figure 2.18: Kinetic inductance of NbTiN as function of the film thickness (blue) and geometric inductance (purple).

low quasiparticle scattering time of NbTiN ($\tau \sim 1$ fs [41]) the resistive losses are orders of magnitude lower than for Nb ($\tau \sim 0.3$ ns [42]). The resistance per unit length of a superconducting coplanar waveguide following the two-fluid model [5, 20, 40, 41] can be expressed as

$$R_l = \frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_2} \omega L_k = \frac{n_n}{n_s} \omega^2 L_k \tau, \quad (2.33)$$

where n_s is the density of cooper pairs and n_n the density of quasiparticles. From BCS theory [5, 43] it is predicted that $n_n/n_s = e^{-1.76T_c/T}$, meaning that at fixed temperature a higher T_c will provide smaller R_l . For a 150 nm thick NbTiN film with the kinetic inductance shown in Fig.2.17 at $T = 4$ K, we estimate $R_l \approx 10^{-7} \Omega/m$ at $f = 1$ GHz. In the case of Nb, the same parameters lead to $R_l \approx 0.2 \Omega/m$. Furthermore, superconducting coplanar resonators have been shown to have a lower attenuation factor for NbTiN compared to Nb [30].

It is usually difficult to have a very accurate estimation of the losses in a transmission line, for this reason it is convenient to include a tunable parameter in the system that can be varied *in-situ*. This is the case of the varactor diode, discussed in sec. 2.4.

2.4 Varactor diode

The varactor diode is a variable capacitor that can be tuned by applying a DC voltage. This allows to adjust the matching circuit easily when placed at the end of the shunt stub. The variable capacitance will change the reactance at the end of the stub and therefore tune the effective admittance at the feed line (Y_{stub1} and Y_{stub2} of Fig. 2.19). The diode

is protected from AC signal by means of a bias-tee (C_d and L_d in Fig. 2.19), but in this section we will ignore it and assume the capacitor is connected to the ground.

In this section, we will discuss two different ways of applying this mechanism: An impedance matching circuit with just one capacitor in series at the end of one of the stubs (sec. 2.4.1) and a circuit with two series capacitors, one at each shunt stub (Fig. 2.4.2).

Figure 2.19: Sketch of double stub tuner impedance matching system with a varactor diode at the end of each of the stubs. The varactor diode is indicated as a tunable capacitor to which a bias voltage V_d is applied. A bias-tee formed by C_d and L_d protects the DC powered diode from AC signal.

2.4.1 Matching with one capacitor

This section is based on the work by S. Hellmuller [25]. In order to match a complex load it is necessary to have 2 variable parameters in the system. In this case, however, the lengths of the stubs are fixed. Hence, the parameters that are tuned to match the load are C_2 , the capacitance at the end of stub 2 and f_0 , the matching frequency. The matching frequency therefore is not a degree of freedom here. For this reason, it is usually convenient to first match analytically the estimated load with the stub lengths at a desired matching frequency and then use the variables C_2 and f_0 to adjust the signal to its optimum point.

In order to have a bigger freedom of tunable parameters, and since the capacitance C_2 cannot be negative, it might be favourable to choose a length of the stub in such a way that we consider the capacitance at the end of it. In other words, we match the system analytically by changing l_1 and l_2 but considering a non-zero C_2 at the end of the stub 2. In this way, the capacitance can increase and decrease from its matching value. The equation for l_2 with a capacitor at the end instead of an open circuit (Eq. 2.35) is derived and explained in Sec. 2.4.2, while the equation that gives the length of the open-ended stub 1, l_1 , follows Eq. 2.17.

To illustrate this idea, let us consider a system with a load impedance that follows the tip-sample system described in section 1.3.3 with values $Z_s \approx 0$, $C_c = 180$ fF, $C_s = 2$ pF, $R_T = 1$ G Ω at a resonance frequency $f_0 = 2$ GHz. The capacitance at the end of stub 2 is $C_2 = 2$ pF. We match the system taking into account the losses created by a SC coplanar waveguide system $\alpha = 0.007 + \alpha_d$ Np/m, where $\alpha_d(f_0) = 0.0012$ Np/m is the undoped silicon substrate attenuation constant that follows Eq. 2.28 with the parameters $\epsilon_r = 11.9$, $\rho = 300$ $\mu\Omega\text{m}$, $\mu_r = 11.68$ (values taken from [44])[§].

Figure 2.20: Reflection coefficient Γ (dB) for the system described in the text above as function of the resonance frequency f_0 and the variation of capacitance δC_2 with respect to the matched capacitance $C_2 = 2$ pF at the end of the second stub, while the first stub is kept open-ended. The arrows point the two minima of Γ at $f_0 = 2.0$ GHz - $\delta C_2 = 0$ pF and $f_0 = 2.02$ GHz - $\delta C_2 = -0.17$ pF.

Figures 2.20 and 2.21 show the reflection coefficient as function of the resonance frequency f_0 and the variation in the termination capacitance of the second stub δC_2 . Both figures are matched at the Z_L load impedance and α described above. However, while the values in Fig. 2.20 are calculated with the same attenuation constant α as the one with which the system is matched, Fig. 2.20 shows the spectrum for different α , $\alpha = 0.05 + \alpha_d$ Np/m for [a] and $\alpha = 0.1 + \alpha_d$ Np/m for [b]. The shift in resonance frequency for one of the two minima [¶] of Γ and δC_2 is shown in Tab. 2.5.

Overcoming the effect of the losses is not the only advantage of the varactor diode implementation. In STM, it can be challenging to determine with precision the capacitances

[§]The extra 0.007 of the attenuation constant is chosen in order to have a slightly bigger bandwidth in the signal of the reflection coefficient minimum in such a way that this is visible enough in Fig. 2.20 for the chosen parameter range.

[¶]There will always be two solutions that match the system, both analytically and numerically. These two solutions come from having a non-zero real component of the load impedance, see Eq. 2.15 and 2.16. This is easier to picture with the Smith chart graph (see Ch. 5 in [22]).

Figure 2.21: Reflection coefficient Γ (dB) as function of the matching frequency f_0 and the variation of capacitance δC_2 with respect to the matched capacitance $C_2 = 2$ pF for the same system as in 2.20. [a] for $\alpha = 0.05 + \alpha_d$ Np/m and [b] where $\alpha = 0.1 + \alpha_d$ Np/m. The arrows point the two minima of Γ at $f_0 = 2.0$ GHz - $\delta C_2 = 0$ pF and $f_0 = 2.02$ GHz - $\delta C_2 = -0.17$ pF for (a) and $f_0 = 2.0$ GHz - $\delta C_2 = 0$ pF and $f_0 = 2.02$ GHz - $\delta C_2 = -0.17$ pF for (b).

α (Np/m)	$0.007 + \alpha_d$ (matched)	$0.05 + \alpha_d$	$0.1 + \alpha_d$	$0.002 + \alpha_d$
f_0 (GHz)	2.0	1.98	1.967	2.053
δC_2 (pF)	0.0	0.14	0.2455	-0.0355

Table 2.5: Change in resonance frequency f_0 and stub-end capacitance variation with respect to $C_2 = 2$ pF, δC_2 , of the minimum of the reflection coefficient Γ for different α . The system is matched at $\alpha = 0.007 + \alpha_d$ Np/m with $C_2 = 2$ pF and $f_0 = 2$ GHz and the parameters described in the main text.

of the junction. If there is a shift in capacitance, the system may not match anymore. For this reason, it is useful to have a tunable parameter while measuring, to match back the load. This idea is depicted in fig. 2.22, where, with the same parameters as for 2.20, the coupling capacitance is varied from the previously matched value $C_c = 180$ fF to 250 fF. To match the impedance with this last value of the coupling capacitance, the varactor diode shifts $\delta C_2 = 0.196$ pF with respect to $C_2 = 2$ pF, and the matching frequency drops to $f_0 = 1.96$ GHz.

2.4.2 Matching with a capacitor at each shunt stub

Taking impedance matching equations 2.15 and 2.16 for two open-ended stub tuners from section 2.2.2, we can modify them in such way that instead of having an open-end they are terminated with a capacitor. This is possible to be done analytically because the termination of the stubs is purely imaginary $Z_{end} = jX_{end}$. It would work in the same

Figure 2.22: (a) Reflection coefficient Γ (dB) as function of the matching frequency f_0 and the variation of capacitance δC_2 with respect to the matched capacitance $C_2 = 2$ pF for the same system as in 2.20. In this case the losses are matched with the lengths ($\alpha = 0.007 + \alpha_d$), but the tip-sample coupling capacitance is varied from 180 fF to 250 fF. The minimum of Γ is found at $f = 1.96$ GHz and $\delta C_2 = 0.196$ pF. (b) Reflection coefficient as function of frequency comparing the cases of $C_c = 180$ fF matched (blue), $C_c = 250$ fF not matched (orange) and $C_c = 250$ fF matched with the varactor diode (green).

way for an inductive termination.

Here we will focus uniquely on deriving the expression of the lengths of the stubs that match a given load with two shunt stubs that end in a capacitor. The equations 2.15 and 2.16 are the same, since they refer to the condition that the susceptance of the stubs at the feedline must fulfill to match the load. However Eq. 2.17 must be modified, given

that the shunt stubs are not open-ended anymore. The matching lengths can be derived from the impedance of each of the stubs at the feedline Z_f ,

$$Z_f = Z_0 \frac{\frac{1}{j\omega C} + jZ_0 \tan \beta l}{Z_0 + \frac{j}{j\omega C} \tan \beta l} \quad (2.34)$$

where C is the capacitance and l the length of each of the stubs. The impedance of the stubs at the feedline is $Z_f = jX_f$, which can be written as a susceptance, $X_f = -1/B_f$. Leaving the subscript f and solving for the length l ,

$$l_i^C = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi} \arctan \left(\frac{1/(wC_i) + \frac{-1}{B_i}}{1/(B_i Z_0 w C_i) + Z_0} \right) \quad (2.35)$$

where $i = 1, 2$ for each stub. If $C_i \rightarrow 0$, we get back Eq. 2.17.

In the same way that we can calculate the lengths for a given capacitance, it is straightforward to derive the equation of the capacitance that matches the load for a given stub length at any desired frequency,

$$C_i = \frac{1}{\omega} \frac{1 - \tan \beta l / (B_i Z_0)}{Z_0 \tan \beta l + 1/B_i} \quad (2.36)$$

where $i = 1, 2$. This equation proves that by controlling the termination impedance of both shunt stubs it is possible to match the Z_L at any desired frequency *in-situ*.

Before implementing a system with a variable frequency, we first aim to study the effects of the diode in the set up at a fixed frequency. The two-diode matching mechanism works in the same way as the double stub length matching, and therefore is not carefully studied in this report.

Conclusions and Outlook

This thesis shows, that if the STM junction is impedance matched at GHz frequencies, RF reflectometry technique can probe the variations of the surface impedance of the sample in the STM junction.

At GHz frequencies, the sensitivity of the total load impedance to changes in Z_s is still very small compared to the variations in stray or coupling capacitive contributions. The efficiency of this method is mirrored in the fact that when scanning a well-cleaved sample at a constant height, the only fluctuations in the signal must come from deviations in the surface sample impedance. Even if changes in Z_s could shift slightly the capacitances due to the proximity of the tip and sample, we would qualitatively probe these variations.

Lumped element circuits provide a practical way to match a given impedance. Even if the inductive and capacitive values vary by 2 – 10% their respective value, they still match the impedance effectively. At GHz frequencies, however, parasitic effects in nH inductors reduce their effective inductance, which complicates determining the right parameters, since higher inductance coils typically have a lower SRF. Furthermore, resistive losses in the circuit may completely dampen the resonance.

At gigahertz frequencies therefore the choice of impedance matching through distributed elements is preferred. The main downside of this method comes from the attenuation constant, which scales with frequency. For this reason, we propose to build a system that minimizes the losses as much as possible: a superconducting coplanar transmission line. Even though the losses are minimized considerably, they will still play a role in the measurement and need to be accurately determined. One possible way to obtain the losses effectively is by measuring a resonator and fitting the signal to obtain α as proposed in [30]. The work by [25] shows that there is yet a second option that allows to compensate for the effect of the losses *in-situ*: A varactor diode. We have seen how by adjusting the capacitance of the diode, we can not only compensate the loss effects, but also the small inaccuracies in the STM junction impedance.

The main advantage that the double stub tuner presents compared to other distributed IM methods is the possibility to have the matching frequency as an adjustable degree of freedom when two varactor diodes are connected to the terminations of the shunt stubs. A system with two varactor diodes has effectively 4 independent parameters that can be tuned: the two lengths of the stubs, which are fixed before the measurement and the two capacitances at the terminations that allow us to match the system at different frequencies while measuring. In this report we show the equations that make possible to match any frequency analytically by tuning the capacitances for fixed lengths of the stubs. This would provide the third free parameter that can be modified when measuring the sample, together with temperature and spatial variability. The possibility to measure the sample surface impedance at different frequencies would yield to a broader knowledge about the properties of the sample.

All in all, radiofrequency impedance matching in STM seems a promising method that can be applied not only to the complex surface impedance study of unconventional and disordered superconductors, but also to a broader range of STM experiments. This could be the case for scanning tunneling noise spectroscopy [45], which measures correlations between electrons by means of the noise coming from discrete charges that tunnel through the STM junction. At higher working frequencies this method would significantly improve its temporal resolution and reduce undesired noise signals.

The work presented in this thesis is purely simulation based and hence the next step would be to build a system experimentally. To this end, the last section of this thesis, sec. 3.1, is dedicated to summarize a possible experimental plan for the stub tuner impedance matching method.

3.1 Experimental plan

Before implementing the stub tuner in the STM, my recommendation is to take some previous steps. Here we present a recipe summarizing the points one might consider to implement the stub tuner system.

Determining α and β

The phase and attenuation constants of a superconducting coplanar transmission line can be accurately determined from the measurements of an undercoupled $\lambda/2$ resonator at the resonance frequency [30]. Measuring at different temperatures will show the temperature dependence of the kinetic inductance. The undercoupled resonator is characterized for having a Q-factor determined by the internal Q of the resonator, $Q_{int} = \beta/(2\alpha)$, while the total Q, $1/Q = 1/Q_{int} + 1/Q_{ext}$. The external Q-factor, Q_{ext} , coming from the capacitive

coupling of the resonator to the feedline, increases by expanding the gap between resonator and feedline.

Using a known load impedance

Once the parameters that characterize the material are known, it is possible to build the circuit. The NbTiN stub tuner is made on chip and this chip placed on a PCB. The first step is to impedance match a very well known system, such as a lumped resistor and capacitor that simulate the tunnel junction impedance. For this, a $500\text{ M}\Omega$ and 2 pF elements are placed in parallel on the PCB and used as load impedance.

Chip fabrication

A 150 nm thick NbTiN on undoped Si substrate is etched via Reactive Ion Etching (RIE). The geometry per unit length is chosen in such a way that the widths of the inner conductor, s , and the gap, w , lay on the $10 - 20\ \mu\text{m}$ range. These widths are chosen on the one hand to avoid losses due to imperfections in the etching when the lengths are too short but also to avoid other type of propagation modes when they are large (see sec. 2.3). The relation between s and w determines the characteristic impedance of the system, which it is aimed at $50\ \Omega$.

Stub tuner measurements

A single varactor diode is used at the end of the second stub. The diode is connected to the stub end and attached to the PCB, close to the bias-tee, and feed by a DC source. Three different systems are measured with the same settings, and if possible, at the same time.

- A system with no load, open-circuited. A stub tuner cannot match an open circuit, hence theoretically there should be no resonance frequency. In practice, however, there might be some parasitic effects from the connections that lead to unwanted resonances that, if they are known, can be neglected when there is a load.
- A stub tuner that matches the load.
- A stub tuner that does not match Z_L and can only be done by tuning the varactor diode's capacitance. In this way, the working efficiency of the diode can be tested in a controlled environment.

Bibliography

- [1] J G Bednorz and K A Müller. Condensed Possible High Tc Superconductivity in the Ba-La-Cu-0 System. *Z. Phys. B-Condensed Matter*, 64:189–193, 1986.
- [2] V. J. Emery and S. A. Kivelson. Importance of phase fluctuations in superconductors with small superfluid density. *Nature*, 374:434–437, 3 1995.
- [3] Mintu Mondal, Anand Kamalpure, Somesh Chandra Ganguli, John Jesudasan, Vivas Bagwe, Lara Benfatto, and Pratap Raychaudhuri. Enhancement of the finite-frequency superfluid response in the pseudogap regime of strongly disordered superconducting films. *Scientific Reports*, 3, 2013.
- [4] J Bardeen, L.N. Cooper, and J. R. Schrieffer. Theory of superconductivity. *Physical Review*, 108(5):1175–1204, 1957.
- [5] Michael Tinkham. *Introduction to Superconductivity*. (Dover Publication Inc., Mineola, New York), 2004.
- [6] Anatoly Larkin and Andrei Varlamov. *Fluctuation Phenomena in Superconductors*. In: Bennemann K.H., Ketterson J.B. (eds) *Superconductivity*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2001.
- [7] A. A. Kordyuk. Pseudogap from ARPES experiment: three gaps in cuprates and topological superconductivity. *Low Temperature Physics*, 41(5), 1 2015.
- [8] B. Keimer, S. A. Kivelson, M. R. Norman, S. Uchida, and J. Zaanen. From quantum matter to high-temperature superconductivity in copper oxides. *Nature*, 518(7538):179–186, 2 2015.
- [9] B. Sacépé, C. Chapelier, T. I. Baturina, V. M. Vinokur, M. R. Baklanov, and M. Sanquer. Disorder-induced inhomogeneities of the superconducting state close to the superconductor-insulator transition. *Physical Review Letters*, 101(15), 10 2008.

-
- [10] B. Sacepe, T. Dubouchet, C. Chapelier, M. Sanquer, M. Ovia, D. Shahar, M. Feigel'man, and L. Ioffe. Localization of preformed Cooper-pairs in disordered superconductors. *Nature Physics*, 7, 12 2010.
- [11] Anand Kamalpure, Tanmay Das, Somesh Chandra Ganguli, Jayesh B. Parmar, Somnath Bhattacharyya, and Pratap Raychaudhuri. Emergence of nanoscale inhomogeneity in the superconducting state of a homogeneously disordered conventional superconductor. *Scientific Reports*, 3, 10 2013.
- [12] Koen M Bastiaans, Damianos Chatzopoulos, Jian-Feng Ge, Doohee Cho, Willem O Tromp, Jan M Van Ruitenbeek, Mark H Fischer, Pieter J De Visser, David J Thoen, Eduard F C Driessen, Teunis M Klapwijk, and Milan P Allan. Direct evidence for Cooper pairing without a spectral gap in a disordered superconductor above T_c . arXiv:2101.08535, 2021.
- [13] D Cho, K M Bastiaans, D Chatzopoulos, G D Gu, and M P Allan. A strongly inhomogeneous superfluid in an iron-based superconductor. *Nature*, 571:541–545, 2019.
- [14] Wei Liu, Minsoo Kim, G. Sambandamurthy, and N. P. Armitage. A dynamical study of phase fluctuations and their critical slowing down in amorphous superconducting films. *Phys. Rev. B*, 84, 10 2011.
- [15] C Julian Chen. *Introduction to Scanning Tunneling Microscopy*. Oxford University Press Inc., 1993.
- [16] Eva. Pavarini, Erik. Koch, Jeroen van den. Brink, George. Sawatzky, Institute for Advanced Simulation., and German Research School for Simulation Sciences. *Quantum materials: experiments and theory*. Lecture notes of the Autumn School on Correlated Electrons 2016, Forschungszentrum Julich, 12-16 September 2016.
- [17] Wei Liu, LiDong Pan, and N. P. Armitage. A broadband microwave Corbino spectrometer at He3 temperatures and high magnetic fields. *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 85, 2 2014.
- [18] J. C. Booth, Dong Ho Wu, and Steven M. Anlage. A broadband method for the measurement of the surface impedance of thin films at microwave frequencies. *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 65(6):2082–2090, 1994.
- [19] Steven M. Anlage, Vladimir V. Talanov, and Andrew R. Schwartz. Principles of near-field microwave microscopy. In *Scanning Probe Microscopy*, volume 2, pages 215–253. Springer New York, 2007.

-
- [20] P. Diener, H. Schellevis, and J. J.A. Baselmans. Homogeneous superconducting phase in TiN film: A complex impedance study. *Applied Physics Letters*, 101(25), 12 2012.
- [21] James Clay Booth. *Novel measurements of the frequency dependent microwave surface impedance of cuprate thin-film superconductors*. PhD thesis, University of Maryland, 1996.
- [22] David M. Pozar. *Microwave Engineering*. John Wiley & Sons Inc., fourth edition, 2011.
- [23] Analog Technologies 0402 Inductor Info. for Super SMT Inductor Kit Specifications.
- [24] Utku Kemiktarak. *Radio-frequency scanning tunneling microscopy: Instrumentation and applications to physical measurements*. PhD thesis, Boston University, 2005.
- [25] Sarah Hellmüller. *Shunt-stub impedance matching circuit for time-resolved reflectometry charge detection in a quantum dot*. PhD thesis, ETH Zurich, 2013.
- [26] Carles Altimiras, Olivier Parlavecchio, Philippe Joyez, Denis Vion, Patrice Roche, Daniel Esteve, and Fabien Portier. Tunable microwave impedance matching to a high impedance source using a Josephson metamaterial. *Applied Physics Letters*, 103(21), 11 2013.
- [27] Rainee Simons. *Coplanar waveguide circuits, components, and systems*. Wiley & Sons Inc., Cleveland, Ohio, 2001.
- [28] W. Fu, M. El Abbassi, T. Hasler, M. Jung, M. Steinacher, M. Calame, C. Schönenberger, G. Puebla-Hellmann, S. Hellmüller, T. Ihn, and A. Wallraff. Electrolyte gate dependent high-frequency measurement of graphene field-effect transistor for sensing applications. *Applied Physics Letters*, 104(1), 1 2014.
- [29] Thomas Hasler. *Microwave Noise Detection of a Quantum Dot with Stub Impedance Matching*. PhD thesis, Universität Basel, Basel, 2016.
- [30] Gabriel Fernando Puebla-Hellmann. *DC, Microwave and Optical Measurement Schemes for Nano-Scale Devices*. PhD thesis, ETH, Zurich, 2013.
- [31] V. Ranjan, G. Puebla-Hellmann, M. Jung, T. Hasler, A. Nunnenkamp, M. Muoth, C. Hierold, A. Wallraff, and C. Schönenberger. Clean carbon nanotubes coupled to superconducting impedance-matching circuits. *Nature Communications*, 6, 5 2015.
- [32] Jiansong Gao. *The Physics of Superconducting Microwave Resonators*. PhD thesis, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, California, 2008.
-

- [33] Frank Schnieder, Thorsten Tischler, and Wolfgang Heinrich. Modeling dispersion and radiation characteristics of conductor-backed CPW with finite ground width. *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, 51(1):137–143, 2003.
- [34] Brian C. Wadell. *Transmission line design handbook*. Artech House, Inc., 1991.
- [35] Koki Watanabe, Keiji Yoshida, Takeshi Aoki, and Satoshi Kohjiro. Kinetic Inductance of Superconducting Coplanar Waveguides. *Japanese Journal of Applied Physics*, 33:5708–5712, 1994.
- [36] Anatolii Polyanskii, Pierre Bauer, Peter J Lee, Cristian Boffo, Leo Bellantoni, Helen Edwards, Alex Gurevich, Matt Jewell, David Larbalestier, G K Perkins, and Alex Squitieri. An Investigation of the Properties of BCP Niobium for Superconducting RF Cavities, 9 2004.
- [37] D. J. Thoen, B. G. C. Bos, E. A. F. Haalebos, T. M. Klapwijk, J. J. A. Baselmans, and A. Endo. Superconducting NbTiN Thin Films with Highly Uniform Properties over a 100 mm diameter Wafer. 9 2016.
- [38] J. M. Graybeal. Competition between superconductivity and localization in two-dimensional ultrathin a-MoGe films. *Physica B+C*, 135(1-3):113–119, 12 1985.
- [39] John Draskovic, Thomas R. Lemberger, Brian Peters, Fengyuan Yang, Jaseung Ku, Alexey Bezryadin, and Song Wang. Measuring the superconducting coherence length in thin films using a two-coil experiment. *Physical Review B*, 88(13), 3 2013.
- [40] K Yoshida, K Watanabe, T Kisu, and K Enpuku. Evaluation of Magnetic Penetration Depth and Surface Resistance of Superconducting Thin Films using Coplanar Waveguides. *IEEE Transactions on applied superconductivity*, 5(2), 1995.
- [41] E. F.C. Driessen, P. C.J.J. Coumou, R. R. Tromp, P. J. De Visser, and T. M. Klapwijk. Strongly disordered tin and NbTiN S-wave superconductors probed by microwave electrodynamics. *Physical Review Letters*, 109(10), 9 2012.
- [42] A. Leo, G. Grimaldi, R. Citro, A. Nigro, S. Pace, and R. P. Huebener. Quasiparticle scattering time in niobium superconducting films. *Physical Review B - Condensed Matter and Materials Physics*, 84(1), 7 2011.
- [43] David Isaac Schuster. *Circuit Quantum Electrodynamics*. PhD thesis, Yale University, 2007.
- [44] Terence Charles Edwards and Michael Bernard Steer. *Foundations for microstrip circuit design*. John Wiley & Sons Inc., 2016.

-
- [45] K. M. Bastiaans, T. Benschop, D. Chatzopoulos, D. Cho, Q. Dong, Y. Jin, and M. P. Allan. Amplifier for scanning tunneling microscopy at MHz frequencies. *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 89(9), 9 2018.

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